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Negative Effects of Heat Stress Conditions during the Hot Summer Season in Egypt on Rabbits Productivity and Alleviation of These Effects Using Some Supplementary Nutrients

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Abstract

Optimal climatic conditions for rabbits would be something like an air temperature of 13 to 20 °C, wind velocity of 5 to 18 km/hr, the relative humidity of 55 to 65% and a moderate level of sunshine and these factors are interrelated. Changes in these environmental factors cause heat stress on rabbits which the animal body has problems dissipating excess heat. In tropical and sub-Tropical countries like Egypt, the climatic characteristic is the major constraint on animal productivity. The summer in Egypt is characterized by high ambient temperature, intense solar radiation and high relative humidity. Therefore, rabbits will be exposed to such severe climatic stress for almost 6 months of the year. Exposure of rabbits to heat stress evokes a series of drastic changes in the biological functions, including a decrease in feed intake, feed efficiency and utilization, disturbances in water, protein, energy and mineral balances, enzymatic activities, hormonal secretions and blood metabolites ending to impairment the productive and reproductive performance. The process of minimizing or reducing these drastic changes in the biological functions in rabbits during the hot summer season is called the amelioration process. Amelioration of heat stress in heat-stressed animals to improve its productivity has been attempted using different techniques including some nutritional means. Vitamins A, D₃ and E are potent antioxidants and rabbits cannot produce these vitamins in their bodies. Therefore an exogenous regular supply is needed to cover the physiological requirements and to sustain high production performance. Vitamin E and Selenim are involved with cellular antioxidant status and the existence of a synergistic action between selenium and vitamin E both improved synergistic antioxidant effect. Oxidative stress commonly occurs following heat stress in tropical regions and negatively affects on animals' performance. The antioxidant activity is high in medicinal plants and antioxidants play an important role in providing protection to animals against heat stress conditions. Ginger lowered lipid peroxidation by maintaining the activities of the antioxidant enzymes. Curcumin or Turmeric has a wide spectrum of biological actions including antioxidant effect due to it acts as a scavenger of oxygen free radicals and lowers the production of reactive oxygen species like superoxide anions, H₂O₂ and nitrite radical which increased when exposure rabbits to heat stress condition.

The present work reviewed the effect of heat stress of hot summer season on the productive and reproductive performance of rabbits and using of different nutritional supplements for alleviating the negative effect of heat stress on rabbits during the hot summer season of Egypt.

Keywords: heat stress, rabbits, nutritional supplements, ginger, curcumin, AD₃Evitamins, vitamin E, selenium.

INTRODUCTION

The temperature of the comfort zone for rabbits is known to be between 13 and 21 °C. The thermal stress on rabbits can be estimated by temperature-humidity index (THI) which combines the effects of ambient air temperature and relative humidity. THI is the most index stress used to evaluate the impact of climatic conditions and to assess the effect of heat stress on livestock production. Rabbits are more susceptible to heat

stress conditions on the reason of their condensed coat and rare functional sweat glands that greatly delay heat loss (Marai et al., 2002a). In recent years, climate change, especially the expected global rise in surface temperature, constitutes a serious hazard on livestock production (Dangi et al., 2016). In tropical and sub-tropical regions like Egypt, heat stress is aggravated with the high relative humidity which is normally over 85% during the day and can reach 100% during the night during the hot months (Marai et al., 2007). At higher temperatures, the rabbits expend energy to maintain their body temperature and re-establishment of the thermal balance. Exposure of rabbits to > 30 THI units or more adversely affects their hormones and trace elements and these drastic changes that occur in biological functions may be responsible for that depression in vitamins and trace elements in blood of heat-stressed rabbits (Habeeb et al., 2018b). The degree of the animal's response to higher ambient temperatures is defined by the animal species and physiological condition (Belhadj Slimen et al., 2015). Heat stress can be definite by a combination of environmental variables or by the sum of forces external to a homeothermic animal that acts to transfer body temperature from its latent state to conditions that are higher than animal's thermoneutral zone (TNZ) (Amici et al., 2010). The heat load increases by exposure to a high environmental temperature that induces rabbits to try to balance the excessive heat load and sustain the homeothermy by using different means to dissipate, as much as possible, the latent heat (Marai et al., 2002b). Alleviations of heat stress syndrome during the hot summer season can be reduced or even eliminate those losses in rabbits. The process of minimizing or reducing these effects is called the amelioration process (Habeeb et al., 2018a). Amelioration of heat stress in heat-stressed animals in order to improve their productivity. Amelioration of heat stress has been attempted using different techniques including nutritional and physiological means.

The present work reviewed the negative effects of heat stress on physiological parameters, blood biochemical components, productive and reproductive performance and using different supplements for alleviating these negative effects on rabbits.

1- Effect of heat stress on physiological parameters:

Rectal temperature (RT) and respiration rate (RR) are parameters which illustrate the mechanism of physiological adaptation (Sharma et al., 2013). Rabbits usually use three devices to modify heat stress: general position, breathing rate and peripheral temperature. It has been demonstrated that rabbit body temperature also increases when the environmental temperature exceeds 28°C (Amici et al., 2010). RT is considered as a good index of body temperature even though there is a considerable variation in different parts of the body core at different times of the day (Srikandakumar et al., 2003). A rise in RT was enough to reduce performance in most livestock species which makes the body sensitive indicator of physiological response to heat stress. Both rectal and scrotal temperatures responded rapidly to elevated air temperature; meanwhile, the scrotal temperature was normally lower than RT by about 1.4°C (Tharwat et al., 1994). RT increased significantly at hot climate 41.1°C compared with 38.5°C under a mild climate of NZW pregnancy rabbits (Abd-Al-Rahman and Baqey, 2016). Particularly, the increased value in RT was estimated to be about 1.0°C when the ambient temperature increases from 18.8°C in winter to 30.7°C in summer (Abdel- Samee et al., 2014). The increase in RT of the heat-stressed rabbits might be due to either poor ability of the animals to prevent the rise in RT or to failure of the physiological mechanisms of animals to balance the excessive heat load caused by exposure to high ambient temperature (Habeeb et al., 1998). When exposure rabbits to high temperatures, animals try to balance the excessive heat load by different means to dissipate as much possible include greater vasodilatation with increased blood flow to the skin surface, sweating and a more rapid respiratory rate (Marai and Habeeb, 1994).

Skin temperature (ST) of NZW rabbits was higher in summer than in winter due to the warmth effect of the coat (Habeeb et al., 2018a). ST is directly affected by body temperature conduction through the blood and other body fluids, in addition to radiation. In this respect, it may be of interest to note that ST was higher by 0.1-0.3°C than RT in summer, while it was almost equal to RT in winter (Habeeb et al., 1998).

The ear lobe temperature is the major physiological process that regulates body temperature against any

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environmental changes (Marai and Habeeb, 1994). When the temperature is above 25-30 °C, the animals stretch out and step their ear to lose as much heat as possible by radiation and convection. The function of the ear lobe in thermoregulation of rabbits is like that of a car radiator. The physiological role of the lobe is through a vasomotor mechanism that controls blood circulation from the body core to the very big meshwork of blood vessels and blood capillaries. The tip region of the ear lobe includes less abundant blood vessels of smaller caliber than those of the middle region and this is the reason that the temperature of the tip region is always lower than in the middle region (Marai et al., 2002a,b). Ear temperature of the rabbits was significantly higher in summer than in winter. Consequently, the ear lobe temperature differs greatly during the different months of the year with an almost similar trend to that of the air temperature (Habeeb et al., 1998).

Rabbits use breathing rate to increase heat loss, therefore respiration rate (RR) is the most important dissipation pathways since most of the sweat glands in rabbits are functional and perspiration (evacuation water through the skin) is never great because of the fur (Marai et al., 2001). At 30°C, latent heat evacuation is only controlled by altering breathing rate and the increase percentages in respiration rate in summer were 42-59% more than the winter average (Habeeb et al., 1998). The significance of the increase in RR is that it enables the animals to dissipate heat by vaporizing high moisture through the respiratory air which accounts for about 30% of the total heat dissipation. The respiration rate values decrease during winter more than that occurs during summer as the age of animals increase (Habeeb et al., 1998). High ambient temperature causes increase in RR and the increase in RR and evaporative water loss is linearly related to the increase in ambient temperature above the panting threshold and thus enables the animals to dissipate heat by vaporizing high moisture through the respiratory air which accounts to about 30% of total heat dissipation (Marai et al., 2007). Respiration becomes the main pathway for loss of the latent heat since most sweat glands in rabbits are not functional and perspiration is not great due to the fur (Marai and Habeeb, 1994).

2- Effect of heat stress on blood biochemical components:

The total plasma proteins (TP) content is affected by the environmental temperature. TP levels in the plasma of heat-stressed NZW rabbits were significantly lower in the heat-stressed group (Ondruska et al., 2011). TP decreased significantly in summer than in winter and the decline values on average were estimated by 6.7% in NZW and Cal rabbits (Marai et al., 1994), 10.9% (El-Masry et al., 1994) and 19.9% (Habeeb et al., 1993). Decreasing total protein in summer may be due to the fact that TP in plasma generates a colloid osmotic pressure which controls the flow of water between blood and tissue fluid (Ondruska et al., 2011). Generally, the decline in blood TP with rising ambient temperature seems to be due to a dilution of TP caused by the increase in water consumed, and/or it could be due to increases in protein utilization and amino acid transamination in the heat-stressed rabbits (Habeeb et al., 1993). In addition, the increase in plasma volume as a result of heat shock may result in decreases TP concentration (Okoruwa, 2014). Moreover, increases in serum cortisol concentrations during elevated temperature exposure might inhibit protein synthesis in tissues and may promote protein catabolism (Okab and El-Banna, 2003).

Blood urea nitrogen concentration in rabbits was found to differ according to the season of the year. Urea nitrogen concentration in rabbits was significantly lower in the summer than in the winter and the percentage decrease values were 15.1% in Cal rabbits (Habeeb et al., 1993) and 9.8% in Cal and 9.2% in NZW (Marai et al., 1994). The depression in blood urea-N associated with heat stress in animals may be due to more reabsorption of the urea-N from the blood to the rumen to compensate for the decrease in ruminal ammonia-N as a result of the decrease in feed intake. In addition, the increase in urinary nitrogen excretion under severe heat stress conditions, as indicated by negative nitrogen balance, may also contribute to the decrease of blood urea levels under such conditions (Habeeb et al., 1992).

Blood creatinine concentration in rabbits as affected by heat stress is conflicting. Some studies showed that it decreases under heat stress conditions and the decline values were estimated at 37.7, 11.4 and 20.6% in Cal rabbits aged 6, 9 and 12 weeks of age, respectively (Habeeb et al., 1993) and 12.8% in NZW and 19.8% in Cal rabbits (Marai et al., 1994). Other studies showed that creatinine concentration increased significant-

ly in rabbits reared under summer than in those reared under winter season conditions (Abdel- Samee et al., 2014).

3- Effect of heat stress on hormonal blood levels:

With long heat exposure, the hypothalamic hormone-releasing factors are suppressed and consequently, the pituitary hormones and other hormones, either autonomous or pituitary controlled, are decreased. The hormonal concentrations are altered by high environmental temperature, particularly, the hormonal secretions are known to be of major importance in productive and reproductive performance (Marai and Habeeb 1994). The thyroid gland secretes tetraiodothyronine (thyroxin) (T_4) and triiodothyronine (T_3) which provide a major mechanism important for acclimation and are known indicators of heat stress (Marai et al. 2004b). It is well known that thyroid hormones, either T_4 or T_3 play an important role in the animal's adaptation to environment changes (Marai and Habeeb, 1998). The drastic changes that occur in biological functions in animals like depression in feed intake and utilization, as well as disturbances in water, protein, energy and mineral metabolism, may be responsible for reducing the secretion of thyroid hormones under heat stress conditions (Habeeb et al., 1992). The low plasma T_3 concentration during the hot period may reflect well the hormonal response of rabbits to prolonged heat exposure and to the marked decrease in feed intake (Boiti et al., 1992). A decline in the blood concentrations of T_3 and T_4 has been reported in heat-stressed rabbits (Abd-Al-Rahman and Baqey, 2016). The negative effect of the hot summer season on some blood hormones, vitamins and trace elements in rabbit bucks was studied by Habeeb et al. (2010). Authors found that hot summer season decreased each of vitamins (B6 and B9), minerals (Se and Zinc) and testosterone hormone significantly and increased cortisol hormone in both blood and semen of rabbit bucks. Testosterone concentrations in both blood plasma and seminal plasma of rabbit's bucks were lower under hot climate than that under mild climate and the decrease percentages due to heat stress were 12.0 and 34.0% in blood plasma and seminal plasma, respectively (Habeeb et al., 2018a). The hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis gets activated in response to heat or climatic stress that consequently increases plasma glucocorticoid concentrations in blood (Habeeb et al., 2018b). Activation of the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis and the consequent increase of blood glucocorticoid concentrations are perhaps the most important responses of animals to stressful conditions (Habeeb et al., 1992). Adrenocortical activity under thermal stress is considered a thermoregulatory protective mechanism is preventing metabolic heat production in a hot environment for animal adaptation to heat stress conditions (Habeeb et al., 1992). Animals respond to stress by releasing ACTH from the anterior pituitary gland which causes the adrenal cortex to release corticosterone (Marai et al. 2004b). In addition, the drastic changes that occur in biological functions in animals may be responsible for increasing the catabolic hormones, especially cortisol (Habeeb et al., 2018b). Habeeb et al. (2018a) found that hormonal cortisol levels actually increased significantly under heat stress conditions in New-Zealand rabbits and attributed that the fact that cortisol is considered thermogenic hormone in heat-stressed animals.

4- Effect of heat stress on feed and water intake:

Daily feed intake decreased from 158.92 g to 67.28 g (42.4%) when New-Zealand rabbits were exposed to elevated temperature (Ondruska et al., 2011). Various authors have reported depression in feed consumption in rabbits (Marai et al., 2007 and 2008 and Okab et al., 2008). Marai et al. (2004a) estimated the decrease in weekly feed intake by 162 g in NZW rabbits during summer compared with winter. Accordingly, the dry matter intake was found to decrease in summer and the decrease was estimated as 46.9% on day 60, 65% on day 90 and 44.4% on day 120 of age when compared with winter. Depression in feed consumption seemed to be the most important reaction to heat exposure. Depression in feed consumption by exposure to elevated heat is due to the fact that environmental temperature stimulates peripheral thermal receptors to transmit suppressive nerve impulses to the appetite centre in the hypothalamus causing the decrease in feed consumption, dry matter intake and consequently fewer substrates become available for enzymatic activities, hormone synthesis and heat production (Habeeb et al., 1998). The exposure to ambient temperatures above the thermal comfort zone has

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a negative impact on animal performance by decreasing feed intake and increasing the feed conversion ratio (Marai et al., 2001).

Digestibility coefficients also declined by 7.9% in dry matter, 8.1% in crude protein and 1.0% crude fibre due to heat stress and the reduction in the digestibility of dry matter and crude protein may be a result of a depression in the production of digestive enzymes due to heat stress (Habeeb et al., 1992).

High ambient temperatures had an increase the water consumption. The high consumption of water during heat stress helps the animals to increase heat loss through the vaporization of water during respiration (Habeeb et al., 1992 and Mousa-Balabel, 2004).

5- Effect of heat stress on productive and reproductive performance:

5.1. Bodyweight:

Growth is a complex set of metabolic events that are genetically and environmentally controlled. Rabbits reared in summer showed a reduction in live body weight and daily body weight gain compared to those reared in winter (Ayyat and Marai, 1997). The exposure to ambient temperatures above the thermal comfort zone has a negative impact on animal performance by decreasing body weight (Marai et al., 2001). Total and daily weight gains in growing NZW rabbits affected negatively by exposure to heat stress (Ondruska et al., 2011). The later authors found that total body weight gain was larger (749.20 ± 14.42 g) in the winter than that in the heat-stressed rabbits (527.90 ± 10.06 g). The reduction in daily gain was due to a drastic decrease in rabbit total feed intake (1412.88 vs. 3337.32 g) and in the feed conversion ratio (2.68 ± 0.05 vs. $4.45 \pm 0.09\%$) compared with the winter group. Marai et al. (2008) found that live body weight and daily body gain weight of NZW male rabbits were significantly lower in summer than in winter and the significant lower final body and daily gain weights during summer were probably due to the lower feed intake (10.4%) and feed conversion (8.3%). This reduction in daily gain may be due to less protein biosynthesis and less fat deposition (Okab et al., 2008). In addition, a decrease in feed intake and feed utilization and the consequent reduction in substrates and hormones are responsible for the depression in gain weight (Habeeb et al., 1992). The feed cost, return and final margin values for growing rabbits were significantly lower in summer than in winter due to the decrease in feed intake and body gain (Marai et al., 2005 and 2008).

Conception rate of doe rabbits appears to be affected by seasonal variations (Ayyat and Marai, 1996). The authors found that exposure of adult female rabbits to severe heat of stress adversely affects their reproductive rates, ovulation rate, number of implantation sites per doe and number of viable embryos per doe. Conception rate was lower in hot summer than in winter by 76.8% (Marai et al., 2001).

5.2. Conception rate:

The low conception rate during the hot conditions may be due to a complex set of events that are expressed in to the adverse effects on growth and reproductive rates and also may be a result of either fertilization failure or early embryonic mortality (Marai et al. (2004a). There are many causes for low conception rates during summer, including reduced oocyte quality (Shehab-El-Deen et al., 2010), failure of fertilization, reduced embryonic development and altered secretion of various hormones (Sartori et al., 2002).

5.3. Litter size and weight:

Litter size is defined as the number of progenies born per parturition. Average litter size can be calculated on a yearly basis to be consistent with the annual rate of fertility. Litter size at birth was found to be affected significantly by the season of kindling and the highest values were recorded during winter and the lowest during summer (Habeeb et al., 1999). The values of litter size at birth as 6.6 kits in winter and 5.8 kits with a reduction of 14% in summer season in NZW rabbits (Ayyat and Marai, 1998). Exposure of NZW doe rabbits to severe heat stress under Egyptian environmental conditions affected negatively significantly on litter size at birth (Abdel-Monem et al., 2016). Litter weight at birth and at weaning was found to be affected by season of kindling. The litter weight at birth was higher during winter than in summer (Farghaly and EL- Darawany, 1994). Exposure of

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rabbits to a high ambient temperature decreases embryonic weight and length (Marai et al., 2001). Significant effects of season on litter weight at birth, at 21 days and at weaning and the lowest values were observed during summer (Marai et al., 2007). Exposure of NZW doe rabbits to severe heat stress conditions affected negatively significantly on litter weight of kits at birth, 21 days and weaning (Abdel-Monem et al., 2016).

Mortality rate:

Pre-weaning total mortality percentage was found to be affected significantly by the season of kindling and was 10.05, 28.99, 46.18 and 12.24% in autumn, winter, spring and summer seasons, respectively (Radwan, 1998). Most studies showed that the highest values of mortality rate percentage were in summer and the lowest percentage was in winter (Habeeb et al., 1999). Averages of pre-weaning mortality rate as 71.9% in summer and 27.3% in winter with an increase of 163.4% in summer (Marai et al., 1996). Pre-weaning mortality rates of 32.2% was during summer and 26.6% were during winter (Bassuny, 1999). The mortality rate from birth up to weaning increased significantly with the increase in ambient temperature from 19.5°C in January to 34.8°C in July and the lowest and highest mortality rate values were recorded on the 1st week in January and on the 4th week in July, respectively. During the post-weaning phase, the mortality rate was 18% in summer while no mortality was recorded during winter (Habeeb et al., 1999). During 5-9, 9-13 and 5-13 weeks of age intervals, mortality rate values were higher in summer and lowered in spring than in autumn and winter (Shehata et al., 1998). The recorded high values for mortality rate in summer may be attributed to the high ambient temperature and direct effect of heat stress on the sensitive offspring, in addition to, a reduction of milk production as well as due to the general depression of metabolic activity in the summer (Habeeb et al., 1999).

Physical semen characteristics:

Semen characteristics vary from season to another and such seasonal variations have been attributed to variation in atmospheric temperature and length of photoperiod. Sperm abnormalities were increased significantly due to exposed rabbits to chronic heat stress (Finzi et al., 1995). Concerning physical semen characteristics, Habeeb et al. (2011) found that ejaculate volume, sperm motility, sperm cell concentration, total sperm output and a number of motile sperms per ejaculate were significantly lower under heat stress than under mild conditions. In contrast, hot conditions increased significantly reaction time, dead sperm%, sperm abnormalities%, and acrosomal abnormalities % (Nizza et al., 2003). Autumn and winter recorded the best semen parameters in terms of sperm concentration, motility of sperms, abnormal sperms and libido relative to spring and summer and the estimates during autumn, winter, spring and summer were 537, 564, 405 and 437 for sperms concentration, 72.0, 68.5, 61.6 and 58.4% for motility of sperms, 7.6, 5.3, 9.6 and 10.2% for abnormal sperms and 4.03, 3.38, 3.51 and 3.04 for libido (AL-Sobayil and Khalil, 2004). Expose to summer season affected in the male rabbit libido were significantly altered (14.8 vs. 7.2 seconds), sperm volume without gel, spermatozoa mobility, viability and concentration by ejaculate decreased significantly, respectively, by 22 % and rabbits exposed to thermal conditions had lower libido and a gel-free volume of ejaculate significantly compared to those subjected to spring ambient conditions (Ain-Baziz et al., 2012). Most authors confirmed this effect using various types of the rabbit under variable summer ambient conditions (Safaa et al., 2008). The decrease in the volume induced by summer ambient temperatures could be related to changes in secreted testosterone levels (Habeeb et al., 2008). The adverse effects of hot summer on semen characteristics could be explained by the degeneration of the germinal epithelium and to the partial atrophy of seminiferous tubules and to defects of the spermatogenesis, particularly, in the last stage of differentiation of spermatids (Theau-Clément et al., 2009).

6- Amelioration the negative effect of heat stress conditions on rabbits:

Amelioration the negative effect of heat stress on rabbits during high environmental temperature has been attempted using different techniques including nutritional and physiological means to improve productive and reproductive performance under heat stress conditions. In this part from the article, the methods of amelioration the negative effect of heat stress on rabbits were discussed using some supplementary nutrients like vitamin E

plus selenium, vitamins AD₃E mixture and some medicinal plants like Curcumin (Turmeric) and Ginger (Zingiber).

6.1. Vitamin E plus selenium:

Selenium (Se) is known to be incorporated in the enzyme glutathione peroxidase performing the antioxidative defence of the body by eliminating hydrogen peroxides and lipid hydroperoxides (McKenzie et al., 1998). Se is involved in immune and neuropsychological function in the nutrition of animals (MacPherson, 1994). Se is also a component of selenoproteins and several selenoproteins have later been identified with functions connected to the thyroid hormone metabolism, testes and sperm function and muscle metabolism (Brown and Arthur, 2001). In addition, Se plays an important role in the growth and health of livestock through its participation in several important enzymes and enzyme reactions (Surai, 2006). Se caused significant improvement in body weight and feed intake in male rabbits (Kamel, 2012).

Vitamin E is required for preventing peroxidation in the particular subcellular membrane which is most susceptible to peroxidation (Institute of Medicine, 2013). Vitamin E also directly alters the thermal set point by decreasing prostaglandin output, especially prostaglandin E series which increases during stress and has a direct effect on the hypothalamic thermoregulatory zone (Hadden, 1987). Vitamin E removes the free radicals which are unstable compounds that damage the cell structure by combining with free oxygen and destroys free radicals (Mayo Clinic, 2013). In addition, immunity levels improve when vitamin E is consumed (Institute of Medicine, 2013). Vitamin E is a fat-soluble antioxidant that prevents oxidation of unsaturated fatty acids and vitamin A in the intestine and acts as an important role in growth, fertility and increases body resistance (National Institutes of Health, 2016).

Selenium has a biological function related to vitamin E. Vitamin E and Se are involved with cellular antioxidant status and increased intake of vitamin E can reduce responses to Se supplementation (Hogan et al., 1990). The existence of a synergistic action between selenium and vitamin E reported, while both improved synergistic antioxidant effect (Kalaba, 2012). Using of vitamin E and selenium in rabbits exposed to heat stress (35°C) for 35 days reduced physiological thermoregulatory parameters comparative with rabbits under comfortable conditions (Al-Zafry and Medan, 2012).

Adding Se with vitamin E to reduce the negative effect of the heat stress conditions on male NZW rabbits was studied by Sharaf et al. (2019a). The addition of Se with vitamin E in the diet of male rabbits improved live body weight, feed intake and increased significantly protein fraction concentrations in the blood serum and decreased water intake and each of rectum, skin and ear temperatures as well as respiration rate compared with rabbits not received Se with vitamin E. The addition also led to significant decreases in the level of cortisol hormone and significant increases in the levels of thyroid hormones (T₃ and T₄) as well as testosterone hormonal and led to significant improvement in the normal sperms, volume, concentration of sperm, sperm motility and live sperms and decreased the percentage of dead sperm. Similar results obtained in the female NZW rabbits (Sharaf et al., 2019b). The addition in the female NZW rabbits led to significant decreases in the level of cortisol hormone and significant increases in the levels of thyroid hormones (T₃ and T₄) as well as progesterone hormonal level and led to significant improvement in each of conception rate, average litter size at birth and at weaning, average litter weight at birth and at weaning, average kits weight at birth and at weaning and decreases the mortality percentage from birth to weaning.

6.2. Vitamins AD₃E mixture:

Vitamin A is required for the normal reproductive process in males of any animals and the deficiency of vitamin A produces a decrease in sexual activity and spermatogenetic disorders (Fennema, 2008). Vitamin D₃ stimulates the absorption of calcium and phosphorus in the intestine performing the function of the carrier of these minerals and regulates these minerals metabolism in the blood (Habeeb et al., 2016). In addition, vitamin D₃ acts on the bone tissue, both on the osteodasts increasing the production of alkaline phosphatase and on osteoblasts stimulating the cell difference and multinucleate (Institute of medicine, 2010). Vitamin E removes

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the free radicals which are unstable compounds that damage the cell structure by combining with free oxygen and destroys free radicals (**Mayo Clinic, 2013**). Vitamins A, D₃ and E are potent antioxidants and animals cannot produce these vitamins in their bodies. Therefore an exogenous regular supply is needed to cover the physiological requirements and to sustain high production performance (**Hafez, 2012**). In addition, supplementation of heat-stressed animals with these vitamin resources is required to correct the protein and energy negative balances during the hot weather season in Egypt (**Habeeb et al., 2015**).

Adding vitamin AD₃E mixture to reduce the negative effect of the heat stress conditions on male New Zealand rabbits was recently studied by **Sharaf et al. (2019a)**. The authors found that the addition improved live body weight and feed intake and decreased water intake as well as thermoregulatory parameters compared with rabbits not received vitamins AD₃E in their diet. In addition, the same authors found that the addition led to significant decreases in the level of cortisol hormone and significant increases in the levels of thyroid hormones (T₃ and T₄) as well as testosterone hormonal. Moreover, the addition led to significant improvement in the normal sperms, volume, concentration of sperm, sperm motility and live sperms and decreased the percentage of dead sperm compared with rabbits not received vitamins AD₃E in their diet. Effect of adding vitamins AD₃E to the diet of female NZW rabbits under heat stress conditions was also recently studied by **Sharaf et al. (2019b)** and reported that the improved live body weight, feed intake and decreased water intake compared with rabbits not received vitamins AD₃E in their diet. The addition also led to significant decreases in the level of cortisol hormone and significant increases in the levels of thyroid hormones (T₃ and T₄) as well as hormonal progesterone levels compared with rabbits not received vitamins AD₃E in their diet. In the same time, the addition led to significant improvement in each of conception rate, average litter size at birth and at weaning, average litter weight at birth and at weaning, average bunny weight at birth and at weaning and decreases the mortality from birth to weaning compared with rabbits not received vitamins AD₃E in their diet.

The improvement in the performance of heat-stressed rabbits treated with AD₃E vitamins may be due to the fact that these vitamins are involved in the synthesis of important coenzymes (NAD and FAD), which are responsible for the biological oxidative process that produces the necessary ATP for protein, fat and carbohydrate biosynthesis (**Habeeb et al., 2018b**).

6.3. Medicinal plants:

Using antibiotics as growth promoters and many artificial feed additives in animal production become international refused due to their adverse and side effects on human health (**Tauheed et al., 2017**). It is indispensable to replace these feed additives with other natural substances that have no effects on animal and human health. Great attention must be focused on using natural feed additives such as herbs and medicinal plants in rabbit feeding (**Habeeb and EL-Tarabany, 2012**). Many medicinal plants can be used as natural growth promoters for improving the productive and reproductive performances of rabbits (**Gupta and Sharma, 2014**). Herbs contain phytoestrogens, which are plant chemicals similar to sex hormones (**Sayed et al., 2005**). It was found that herbs' volatile oil can diffuse into the sperm cells membrane and serve as an intracellular structure (**Manjunatha and Srnivasan, 2006**).

6.3.1. Curcumin (Turmeric)

Curcumin is extensively used as a spice, food preservative and colouring material. The main yellow bioactive component of Curcumin has been shown to have a wide spectrum of biological actions including antioxidant, anticoagulant, antifertility, antibacterial, antifungal, antiprotozoal and hypocholesterolemic activities (**Chattopadhyay et al., 2004**). The biological activity of Curcumin is due to its antioxidant effect. The antioxidant activity is due to it acts as a scavenger of oxygen free radicals and protects hemoglobin from oxidation (**Shen et al., 2007**). Curcumin increases the antioxidant enzymes superoxide dismutase, catalase and glutathione peroxidase levels in the blood. In addition, Curcumin prevents oxidative damage during indomethacin-induced gastric lesions not only by blocking inactivation of gastric peroxidase, but also OH (**Chattopadhyay et al., 2004**). Curcumin lowers the production of reactive oxygen species like superoxide

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anions, H₂O₂ and nitrite radical generation by maintaining the activities of antioxidant enzymes like superoxide dismutase, catalase and glutathione peroxidase (Swatson et al., 2017). Recent studies indicated that curcumin could ameliorate high glucose-induced neural defects by suppressing cellular stress and apoptosis (Wu et al., 2015).

Practically, recently **Habeeb et al. (2019)** studied the effect of adding curcumin in the diet at the rate of 250 mg /doe/day to reduce the negative effect of the heat stress conditions of the hot summer season on female NZW rabbits. Authors found that improved body weight and feed intake and decreased water intake and also led to significant decreases in the level of cortisol hormone and significant increases in the levels of thyroid hormones (T₃ and T₄) as well as progesterone hormonal level compared with rabbits not received curcumin in their diet. In the same time, the addition led to significant improvement in each of conception rate, average litter size at birth and at weaning, average litter weight at birth and at weaning, average bunny weight at birth and at weaning and reduction in the mortality rate from birth to weaning compared with rabbits not received curcumin in their diet.

6.3.2. Ginger (Zingiber)

Ginger increases the motility of the gastrointestinal tract and have analgesic, sedative, antipyretic and antibacterial properties in animals (Wohlmuth, 2008). Ginger lowered lipid peroxidation by maintaining the activities of the antioxidant enzymes superoxide dismutase, catalase and glutathione peroxidase and increased blood glutathione (Ahmed et al., 2000). Many authors reported that pharmacological effects of Zingiber officinale rhizomes include antipyretic, antihypertensive, antihyperlipidaemic, anti-inflammatory and immunestimulant properties (Young et al., 2005 and Goyal and Kadnur, 2006).

Feeding diets containing ginger to growing NZW rabbits increased significantly body weight gain, dressing percentage and carcass traits as well as increased significantly net revenue and relative economic efficiency (Ibrahim, 2010). The same authors reported that adding ginger to the diet of rabbits increased significantly kindling rate and decreased gestation length significantly. Practically, recently **Habeeb et al. (2019)** studied the effect of adding Ginger in the diet at the rate of 250 mg /doe/day to reduce the negative effect of the heat stress conditions of the hot summer season on female NZW rabbits. Authors found that the addition of ginger reduced the thermoregulatory parameters on the female rabbits by decreasing the rectum, skin and ear temperatures as well as respiration rate compared with rabbits not received ginger in their diet. The same authors found that the addition improved body weight, feed intake and protein fraction concentrations in the blood serum and decreased water intake compared with rabbits not received ginger in their diet. In addition, ginger also led to significant decreases in the level of cortisol hormone and significant increases in the levels of thyroid hormones (T₃ and T₄) as well as hormonal progesterone levels compared with rabbits not received ginger in their diet. In the same time, the addition led to significant improvement in each of conception rate, average litter size at birth and at weaning, average litter weight at birth and at weaning, average bunny weight at birth and at weaning and reduction in the mortality rate from birth to weaning compared with rabbits not received ginger in their diet.

The improvements in bunny body weight gain of female rabbits that received ginger in their diet during lactation period may be attributed to increased feed intake and feed conversion and, milk yield, and to enhancement in the metabolism of essential and volatile oils included in medicinal plants (Habeeb et al., 2019). In addition, the improvements in body weight gain of female rabbits that received ginger in their diet may also be due to the effect of antimicrobial properties of medicinal plants (Tipu et al., 2006 and Jiang et al., 2006). Total and live litter size at birth and conception rate of females mated with rabbit bucks supplemented orally with 150 and 250 mg/kg body weight extract of ginger was improved significantly compared with that not received extract of Ginger (El-Speiy and El-Hanoun, 2013). Feeding diets containing 1% ginger to NZW rabbit does increase significantly litters size and weight from birth to weaning and increases significantly mean bunny weight and bunny weight gain at different ages from birth to weaning day and decreased significantly mortality rate from birth to weaning (Ibrahim, 2016).

6.3.3. Importance of adding medicinal plants in the diet of heat-stressed rabbits:

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Oxidative stress commonly occurs following heat stress in tropical regions and affects animals' performance (Sariano, 2012) negatively. The adverse effect of the heat stress had a negative impact on glutathione, ATP-ase and cholinesterase enzyme activities. Glutathione is an antioxidant in animals that protects cells from oxidative damages and is capable of preventing damage to important cellular components caused by reactive oxygen species such as free radicals, peroxides, lipid peroxides, and heavy metals (**Habeeb, 2018a**). The ATP-ase and cholinesterase enzymes take the major role in metabolic pathways inside the living cell. There were a significant inhibition of total ATP-ase activity, cholinesterase and glutathione enzymes in animals under heat stress conditions (**Habeeb, 2018b**). The antioxidant activity is high in medicinal plants and antioxidants play an important role in providing protection to animals against heat stress conditions (**Ibrahim 2005 and Ibrahim et al., 2009**).

Conclusion

Exposure of rabbits to heat stress evokes a series of drastic changes in the biological functions which include a decrease in feed intake, feed efficiency and utilization, disturbances in water, protein, energy and mineral balances, enzymatic activities, hormonal secretions and blood metabolites ending to impairment the productive and reproductive performance. The reduction of heat stress syndrome during the hot summer season can be reduced or even eliminate those losses in rabbits production. Adding a solution of Se plus vitamin E or AD3E vitamins mixture to drinking water as well as supplement the ginger or curcumin to rations may minimize the impact of the hot summer season of Egypt on male and female rabbits and succeed in alleviating the adverse effects of heat stress conditions on productive and reproductive parameters of rabbits.

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